

On the Measurement of the Absolute Rates of Migration of Ions by the Method of Moving Boundaries. Part I.

BY JNANENDRANATH MUKHERJEE, RAMPRASAD MITRA AND
ANIL KUMAR BHATTACHARYYA.

The method of moving boundaries has been extensively adopted for determination of transference numbers of electrolytic ions (*cf.* MacInnes and Longworth, *Chem. Reviews*, 1932, **11**, 171).^{*} The absolute rate of migration of an ion can be obtained by the boundary method if the potential gradient under which it moves can be accurately measured. This principle is utilised in the measurement of the cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles by the boundary method. Mukherjee (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, **A**, 103, 102; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, **2**, 296; *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 595; *Kolloid-Z.*, 1932, **58**, 155) has discussed the errors in the procedures previously adopted and has devised a method, based on considerations of disturbing effects arising out of migration of ions at the boundary, which makes it possible to determine the cataphoretic speeds under known potential gradients at and near the boundary. The present paper deals with an application of the method to determination of absolute rates of migration of electrolytic ions. The method allows also to ascertain the changes taking place near the boundary and to compare the results with standard mobility data.

Theory underlying the Method.

Let us consider a boundary between a solution of hydrochloric acid and an equiconducting solution of picric acid (*vide* Fig. 1.). When a potential gradient acts across the boundary in the direction indicated, an adjustment of the concentration of the picric acid takes place such that a more dilute solution of concentration c' , governed by the relation $c/T = c'/T'$, rises. c and c' denote the concentrations and T and T' the transference numbers respectively of the chloride and picrate ions. The concentration c remains unaltered.

^{*} This paper gives a complete bibliography on the subject.

Under steady conditions let A and B be two fixed planes at right angles to the current, respectively in the upper hydrochloric and the lower picric acid solutions. Since the adjusted concentration of the picric acid layer is determined by the concentration of hydrochloric acid layer, the potential difference between the two planes, is given by

$$V = i \left[\sigma_1 (X - x) + \sigma_2 \cdot x \right] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where i , is the constant current density employed ; σ_1 and σ_2 are, respectively the specific resistances of layers of hydrochloric and picric acid solutions ; x is the distance between the boundary and the fixed plane in picric acid and X , the total distance between the planes.

From equation (1)

$$\left(\frac{\delta v}{\delta x} \right) = i (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) = P \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

and
$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\delta v}{\delta t} &= i (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \frac{\delta x}{\delta t} \\ &= i (\sigma_2 - \sigma_1) \times \text{the velocity of the boundary} \\ &= Q \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

P and Q are constants independent respectively of the position of the boundary and time.

Also, the potential gradient in the picric acid layers, is given as,

$$i \cdot \sigma_2 = i \cdot \sigma_1 + \frac{\delta v}{\delta x} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

It is possible to measure the potential gradients in both layers without measuring the cross section of the tube if the potential gradient $i \sigma_1$ in the hydrochloric acid layer and $\delta v / \delta x$ are directly measured.

It follows from the above equations that if there are no disturbing effects, *e.g.* those arising from heating and diffusion, then

(i) the potential difference between the two planes should change linearly with time and also with the distance traversed by the boundary;

(ii) the distance swept should be linearly related with time.

FIG. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL

Mukherjee's apparatus (Fig. 1) for measuring cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles has been used. Rising boundaries between hydrochloric acid of different concentrations and picric acid solutions of correspondingly adjusted concentrations were investigated. The mobility of the picrate ion, as given in the literature, varies rather widely and is about half of that of the chlorine ion. The initial picric acid concentrations that have been used are exactly half of that of the hydrochloric acid solution. Picric acid exhibits a strong colour even in high dilutions and the boundary could be accurately located with the help of a selected light filter. The current from the main was tapped through a voltmeter and maintained constant within 1% by hand regulation of specially constructed adjustable resistances, R_1 . An accurate ammeter directly reading upto 0.0001 amperes, placed in series with the measuring tube, indicated directly within 1% of the current employed. The electrodes, through which the current entered and left the moving boundary cell, were placed in bulbs attached to either limb of the

U-tube. This prevented products of electrolysis from coming in contact with the solution in the **U-tube**. The boundary was formed as with colloidal solutions. In view of irregularities of cross section near the regions where the side-tubes are sealed, the boundary was always formed well above the side-limb 3 and the observation discontinued when it came sufficiently near the side-tube 2. Fairly wide tubes were used so that the electro-osmotic pressure developed on the passage of the current could be neglected.

Method of Calculation.

When the boundary is located between the side-limbs 2 and 3 (*cf.* Fig. 1) the difference in potential between two Ag—AgCl electrodes dipped into the side limbs 1 and 2 is measured. This potential difference remains constant within 0.2%. Knowing the effective distance between these side-limbs, the potential gradient in the upper hydrochloric acid is measured in the manner described previously (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*). As the boundary rises the P. D. between 2 and 3 increases chronologically. The increment corresponding to a given displacement of the boundary is measured, from which the increment per centimetre displacement can be calculated; on adding this increment to the constant potential gradient obtaining in the upper HCl layer, the gradient in picric acid is obtained. By combining these gradients with the distance traversed by the boundary in a given interval of time, the absolute rates of migration of the chloride and also the picrate ions are obtained. The effective distance between the side-tubes was measured in the manner described previously. The values obtained agree within 1.73% : 2.90 and 2.95 cm. between 1 and 2. The two values were obtained by using 0.01N and 0.002N-HCl solutions. The difference is partly due to the fact that when the resistance of the electrolyte is high, apart from troubles due to dielectric leakage, the electrolyte in the immediate neighbourhood of the electrodes does not uniformly take part in the conduction (Mukherjee, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, 36, 595).

Satisfactory Boundary Conditions.

For a satisfactory measurement by this method the boundary must be *sharp and horizontal to start with*. The ideal condition of a perfectly sharp boundary is not always easy to attain in view of dis-

turbances due to heating and diffusion at the boundary. The initial condition of the boundary is an important factor. Thus if the two liquids get mixed owing to filling the tube too rapidly, the restoring effect on passing the current is often not sufficiently strong to make the boundary adequately sharp. The strength of the current to be employed for this purpose is necessarily limited by the heating effects. In these measurements dilute solutions (particularly in the case of 0.002N-HCl and 0.001N- picric acid) present the greatest difficulties in keeping the boundary horizontal. It has a tendency to become convex upwards. In extreme cases the passage of the current is accompanied by a chimney-shaped column of picric acid emerging from the boundary and penetrating deep into the upper liquid; similar phenomena have been observed by MacInnes, Cowperthwaite and Huang (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **49**, 1710) with rising boundaries between KCl and KMnO_4 solutions. Disturbances owing to the above effect were much less prominent when the current was gradually increased to its final value.

The $V-x$, $V-t$, and $x-t$ Curves.

The accompanying curves I—X show that the value for $\delta v/\delta x$, $\delta x/\delta t$ and $\delta v/\delta t$ are not exactly constant as required by the equations (2) and (3). The discrepancy must be referred to the disturbing influences at the boundary owing to which the conditions implied in the linear equations are not satisfied.

Results.—The results of experiments which satisfied the criteria for satisfactory boundary conditions are given in Table I. The first column gives the combination; the second, the potential gradient in volt/cm. in the hydrochloric acid layer between side-limbs 1 and 2, the boundary was always initially formed between side-limbs 2 and 3; the third column gives the potential gradient in layers of picric acid calculated from equation (4), $\delta v/\delta x$ being obtained from the slope of the corresponding curve; the fourth column gives the mobilities (in cm./sec. per volt/cm.) of the Cl' ion calculated from the constant potential gradient in the hydrochloric acid layer and the distances traversed by the boundary in successive known intervals of time; the fifth column gives the chloride ion mobility in cm./sec. per volt/cm. calculated from the measured potential gradient in HCl and the average velocity of the boundary given by the corresponding $x-t$ curve. The sixth column gives the values of the picrate ion mobility (in cm./sec. per volt/cm.) calculated from measurements of distances

traversed by the boundary in successive known intervals of time and the corresponding potential gradients in picric acid layers. The last column gives the picrate ion mobility (in cm./sec. per volt/cm.) calculated by combining the graphically calculated average potential gradient in picric acid layers behind the boundary and the average velocity of the boundary given by the slope of the corresponding $x-t$ curve.

TABLE I.

Temperature = $35 \pm 0.25^\circ$.

Combination.	Pot. gradient.		$v_{cl}' \times 10^5$		$v_{p'} \times 10^5$	
	in HCl.	in HP (from graph).	(calc.)	(from graph).	(calc.)	(from graph).
I*. 0.01N-HCl, 0.005N-HP	0.8658	1.78	79.4 78.6	78.5	38.01 39.36	39.3
II. 0.01N-HCl, 0.005N-HP	0.8688	1.81	80.8 80.2	80.6	38.18 38.7	38.7
III. 0.01N-HCl, 0.005N-HP	0.8545	1.77	80.2	80.0	38.65	38.4
IV. 0.005N-HCl, 0.0025N-HP	1.330	2.67	84.3 84.1	84.2	41.5 42.5	41.9
V. 0.005N-HCl, 0.0025N-HP	1.332	2.69	84.0 84.3	84.3	42.3 44.8	42.7
VI. 0.005N-HCl, 0.0025N-HP	1.224	2.35	83.3 81.9 81.2	82.5	42.5 42.4 45.4	42.1
VII. 0.005N-HCl, 0.0025N-HP	1.223	2.26	82.5 82.2	82.6	41.9 51.0	44.7
VIII. 0.005N-HCl, 0.0025N-HP	0.8081	1.69	81.9 80.7	80.5	40.01 36.70	38.6
IX. 0.002N-HCl, 0.001N-HP	1.003	2.08	86.8 81.2	86.0	41.1 49.1	41.5
X. 0.002N-HCl, 0.001N-HP	1.058	2.13	89.4 82.6	88.2	43.3 45.3	43.6

DISCUSSION.

The method here adopted should give a more direct information of the boundary conditions than the usual method. Also, it enables one to calculate the rates of migration of both the leading and the indicator ions.

* The curves are correspondingly numbered.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

The results show that in a particular measurement the mobility of the chloride ion calculated from chronological observations of the displacement of the boundary tends to decrease while the picrate ion mobility tends to increase. At the same time the slopes of the corresponding $V-x$ and $x-t$ curves show a general tendency to decrease; $\delta v/\delta x$ and $\delta x/\delta t$ tend to decrease with time. The decrease in chloride ion mobility and the simultaneous increase in the mobility of the picrate ion would at first suggest that the hydrochloric acid is becoming concentrated and the picric acid diluted so that the boundary separates two pure layers of hydrochloric and picric acids; the chlorine and the picrate ions in these layers move under potential gradients obtaining in them.

FIG. 4.

Kohlrausch's theory, however, contemplates no changes in the concentration of the leading solution. Besides, such changes cannot account for the diminution of $\delta v/\delta x$ observed by us. In the neighbourhood of adjusted concentrations, if the current remains constant and disturbances arising from thermal and gravitational convection are absent, a sharp boundary has been observed to move (MacInnes and Longworth, *Chem. Reviews*, 1932, 11, 171) with a constant velocity for fairly long intervals of time. In the present case the boundary slows down though the decrease is much less pronounced than the decrease in $\delta v/\delta x$. If the electrolysis be continued for a sufficient length of time the boundary becomes diffuse and hazy.

FIG. 5.

The decrease of $\delta v/\delta x$ for a constant current density connotes the following possibilities (*vide* equation 2).

1. σ_{HCl} increases, σ_{HP} remaining constant,
2. σ_{HP} decreases, σ_{HCl} remaining constant,
3. σ_{HP} decreases, and σ_{HCl} increases.

Since the potential gradient between side-limbs 1 and 2 remains constant and the values of the calculated mobility of the Cl' ion decrease, the first possibility is excluded. The gradual increase of the calculated mobilities of the picrate ions also excludes the second possibility and consequently the third. The cause of the variation of $\delta v/\delta x$ should, therefore, be sought in the boundary itself. A mixed layer whose thickness gradually increases is perhaps responsible for the progressive diminution in $\delta v/\delta x$. But since the velocity of the boundary itself gradually slows down, it is necessary to assume that the potential gradient at the boundary diminishes; that is, the layer becomes more conducting and more concentrated in electrolytes. This would also explain the diminution in the calculated mobilities of the Cl' ion. It should be mentioned however, that *the boundary remains sharp during the period of observation which has been utilised in calculating the data given in the table.* This may not prevent slight mixture brought about by thermal convection or by diffusion. The mobility of the chlorine ions calculated as above would in that case be determined by their speed in this mixed layer. The values would thus be smaller than the actual mobility because a higher potential gradient, namely that in the pure HCl layer has been used in the calculation.

Reference should be made here to the fact that the introduction of the current at first makes the boundary sharp but as the electrolysis proceeds sufficiently long, the boundary becomes hazy. It may, therefore, be assumed that the restoring effect is initially sufficient but that the heating effect of the current produces thermal convection and increased diffusion which nullifies the restoring effect. It is thus possible that even during the earlier period, during which the recorded observations were made, a mixed layer of the two electrolytes was present.

The existence of such a mixed layer whose thickness and concentration gradually increase would explain the chronological increase in the values of the picrate ion mobility. For, the potential gradient

FIG. 6.

obtained from equation (4) used in the calculation would then be progressively smaller ($\delta v/\delta x$ gradually decreases) than the gradient under which the anion moves. We are assuming that the boundary, whose displacement we observe, is situated just inside the mixed layer. The presence of such a mixed layer of higher total ionic concentration than that of the hydrochloric or picric acid layers may, however, lead to other complications which are being ignored for the present.

The above considerations show that the mobilities calculated from the initial slopes $\delta v/\delta x$ and $\delta x/\delta t$ are the most reliable and a comparison should be made only amongst them. The third column of Table II gives the observed (mean) chlorine ion mobility ($F \times v_{Cl'}$) in

hydrochloric acid whose strength in normality is given in column 1. The fourth column gives the theoretical value at the corresponding HCl concentration calculated from Onsager's equation* assuming 92.6** as the limiting Cl' ion mobility at 35°; the fifth column gives the percentage deviation of the observed mean value from the calculated value; the sixth column gives the observed mean picrate ion mobility (in cm./sec. per volt/cm.) in the corresponding picric acid solution. In view of different limiting picrate ion mobilities and also of different temperature coefficients given in the literature, similar comparison of observed with calculated values is not possible.

TABLE II.

HCl conc.	$v_{Cl'} \times 10^5$.	$v_{Cl'}$		% Dif.	$v_{P'} \times 10^5$.
	(obs.)	mean $F \times v_{Cl'}(\text{mean})$	calc.		(Obs. mean).
0.01N	79.4	77.4	87.0	12.4	38.3
	80.8				
	80.2				
0.005N	84.3	80.4	88.8	10.4	41.6
	84.0				
	83.3				
	82.5				
	81.9				
0.002N	86.8	85.1	90.3	6.1	42.2
	89.4				

The observed Cl' ion mobilities are distinctly lower. The discrepancy appears to be greater for concentrated than for dilute solutions though initial satisfactory boundary conditions were more easy to attain in the former cases. Higher current densities had to be employed to obtain sharp boundaries with the concentrated solutions; the higher concentrations would produce more rapid diffusion.

* $\lambda = \lambda_0 - \left[\frac{5.78 \times 10^5}{(DT)^{\frac{3}{2}}} \lambda_0 + \frac{29.5}{(DT)^{\frac{1}{2}\eta}} \right] \sqrt{2C}$, where λ_0 , D , T , η and C are respectively the limiting mobility, the dielectric constant of the solvent, the absolute temperature, the viscosity of the solvent and the equivalent concentration.

** $V_{Cl'}^\infty$ at 25° (Ferguson and Vogel, *Phil. Mag.*, 1927, 4, 940) = 76.63; assuming a temperature coefficient of 2.16% (Newman, "Electrolytic Conduction", 1930, p. 49) it is 92.6 at 35°.

The mobilities appear to depend on the potential gradient in the hydrochloric acid layer though Kohlrausch's theory contemplates no effect of the current provided that the restoring effect is strong enough to give a sharp boundary. MacInnes and Smith (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 1246) and Cady and Longworth (*ibid.*, 1929, **51**, 1656) made similar observations but no explanation of this effect of the current has been given. The calculated mobility is less, the less the potential gradient in hydrochloric acid. Since the heating effect is comparatively small the lower value perhaps indicates that the restoring effect of the weaker current is insufficient to prevent diffusion. The current density is thus a very important factor.

The above discussion suggests that the moving boundary method should give better results when the displacement of the boundary is utilised in the calculation. The speed of the boundary $\delta x/\delta t$ changes much less than $\delta v/\delta x$ and methods which depend on the boundary speed alone, would be free from the errors arising out of the uncertainties regarding the potential gradient obtaining at the boundary. In measuring the cataphoretic speeds of colloidal particles by the method here adopted, the above errors are practically eliminated by choosing the upper liquid such that the potential gradient across the boundary remains constant during both the upward and downward movements (Mukherjee, *loc. cit.*, also *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1932, **36**, 595).

It appears that diffusion and thermal convection affect the thickness of the boundary as also its rate of motion and that for a constant current the mixed layer does not move with the same speed as the 'fully formed boundary.' These observations are not in agreement with those of MacInnes and Longworth (*loc. cit.*).

It is hoped to revert to the points referred to above when experiments now in progress are completed.